

ANALYSIS OF THE MEANINGS OF THE WORD

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ANNOTATION: In this article, there are opinions and comments on the level of significance of the units expressed in terms of the places of use of words in their own and figurative meanings, and with words used in figurative sense. The different communicative aspects of meaning transfers are explained. According to the expression of the words in their meaning, the importance of the analytical compounds is expressed in terms of the structurally understood parts of the meaning in terms of part and part relationships. It is also significant in the article that the expressiveness of words in their original and figurative meanings is explained by the fact that the phenomena of monosemy and polysemy are explained.

KEY WORDS: Monosemy, polysemy, communication

In our human society, the forms of communication between the speaker and the recipient are related to the construction of the communication between the speaker and the recipient, as a certain cause and means, in proportion to the communication of organic connection and their own and portable, in many senses. There are views on its application. Also, it can be said that the place of use of words also serves to express figurative meanings. It can be said that in such cases, when the teacher in his pedagogical activity gives students insights on the use of words in figurative meanings, the technology of explanation, which effectively uses real evidence and examples, gives a good effect. For example: the ear of the pot is the ear of the wall. "In linguistics, it is important to study the feature of polysemy. Because polysemous words are of great importance in enriching the expressive possibilities of the language, expressing different meanings from the meaning of the word through the transfer of meaning by means of various methods.

Compound words have figurative meanings in addition to their meaning. The meaning of a word expressed outside of speech, that is, in language, is called its own meaning. For example: when the words eye and hem are used alone, their original meaning is understood. The word is one of the important elements of the language, and it is formed by a set of sounds and sounds united within a certain meaning. Words in a language can have one or more than one meaning. The phenomenon of unequivocal meaning is called monosemy, and the phenomenon of polysemy is called polysemy".[1] In fact, the use of certain technologies is of great importance in learning and teaching the phenomena of single and multiple meanings of words. In the course of the analysis, the teacher should pay attention to the literal and figurative meanings of the word and not be distracted by phenomena such as homonymy and synonymy.

The uniqueness and attractiveness of the language is explained by the different meanings of the words used in different places. Accordingly, the phenomenon of using words in their own and figurative meanings can be understood from the context text and meaningful unity, idea

of the expressed topic. It is observed that the words used figuratively are used in the composition of artistic texts or dramatic stage works in most cases. In terms of the use of pedagogues in style associations in native language classes or in native language teaching, it is also appropriate for experts to interpret the words that express figurative meaning.

"In linguistics, the only event that gives rise to polysemous words is the event of formation of figurative meaning. In fact, the formation of figurative meaning is one of the main events for the emergence of polysemy. Some linguists consider the phenomenon of meaning expansion to be one of the causes of polysemy. However, this opinion cannot be agreed. Because the occurrence of polysemy is the result of the formation of more than one lexical meaning, the expansion of meaning is only an internal change of one meaning. Linguists note that they are separate semantic phenomena. That is, if a polysemous word is formed due to the occurrence of more than one lexical meaning in one word, the expansion of meaning occurs only within a certain meaning. The scope of the concept of that meaning will expand, and no new meaning will be added to it".[2] Regarding the expressed thoughts, it can be said that during the speech of people, in many cases, figurative words are expressed without explanation. In this case, words are also understood from the point of view of their use in sarcastic places or from the point of view of warning meanings. Compliment of traditional units from the point of view of structural units of understood meaning and technological units.

Cleanliness is also important. For example: the words expressed in the sentences of the eyes of a person and the eyes of a business rely on different meanings. In one of them, a person and an object belonging to him, i.e., a member of the body, are understood, and in the other, the meaning of performing tasks with diligence is understood. It can be mentioned that the following is manifested in the expression of native and figurative meanings of words used in native language textbooks.

1. Paying attention to the use of words;
2. Differentiate between native and figurative meanings;
3. Understanding and understanding with the help of examples;
4. Understanding of the concept of part and whole;
5. Understand and understand the properties of renaming;
6. Understanding the importance of ironic interpretation;
7. Understanding the characteristic between things;
8. Expression of structural functions of words;
9. Place of use and importance of words;
10. Expression of words used in their meaning.

"We have also come to the synecdoche type of the method of transferring meaning. Synecdoche "synecdoche" means understanding together. Synecdoche is the method of transfer of meaning in words based on the expression of part through the whole and the whole through the part. For example: "I cut my hand" means a finger, since the finger is a part of the hand, it means a part through the whole, and in this sentence, "we multiply hooves" means animals. is holding, because the hoof is a part of the animal, it means the whole through the part, or else "enter the door, guest, let's have a chat" in this sentence, the word that changed its meaning is the word "door" enter the door" he means his house. Since the door is a part of the house, the whole is meant by the part. The meaning changes according to the relationship in synecdoche qui.

1. Through body parts. Do not put your hands in your mouth.

2. Through clothing and its parts. He loses his lost pocket in his account".[3]

References:

1. Kurbaniozov Gulmirza, Jalilov Sadaddin. Practical Uzbek language. Nukus "Nur-Turan-Print" 2023.
2. Davidov Yunus Jumayevich. Ways of the phenomenon of polysemy. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL-2022
3. Shermamatova S, Sobirova Nilufarkhan, Nazirova Zebokhon. Methods of transferring meaning in Uzbek: Metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, task. Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences - 2023